

(I.a) Project	(I.b) Participant(s)	(I.c) Date
(II) What means "success" in your project?		

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(III) Objectives/Motivations (O)		(IV) Stakeholders (S)		(V) Deliverables (D)		(VI) Impacts/Outcomes/Benefits (I)									
What are the project's objectives/motivations?		Who are the project's stakeholders?		What are the project's deliverables?		What are the expected impacts/outcomes/benefits?									
ID	Objective/Motivation	Description	ID	Stakeholder	Description	ID	Impact/Outcome/Benefit	Description							
O1			S1			D1									
O2			S2			D2									
O3			S3			D3									
O4			S4			D4									
O5			S5			D5									
(VII) Criteria (C)		(XII) Time frames		e.g., EX ANTE (identify time frame)		1 - e.g., Project Planning (identify time frame)		2 - e.g., Project Executing (identify time frame)		3 - e.g., Project Closing (identify time frame)		e.g., EX POST (identify time frame)			
How success can be measured?				(III) Objectives/Motivations (O)											
ID	Criterion			Description	(IV) Stakeholders (S)										
C1					(V) Deliverables (D)										
C2					(VI) Impacts/Outcomes/Benefits (I)										
C3					(VII) Criteria (C)										
C4					(IX) Success Factors (F)										
C5															
(VIII) Dependencies (D)				(VIII) Dependencies (D)											
There are any external dependencies?				(X) Ethical/Legal Concerns (E)											
ID	Dependency	Description	(XI) Barriers/Obstacles/Challenges (B)												
D1			Notes (N)												
D2															
D3															
D4															
D5															
(IX) Success Factors (F)		(X) Ethical/Legal Concerns (E)		(XI) Barriers/Obstacles/Challenges (B)		Notes (N)									
What are the success factors?		There are any ethical or legal concerns?		There are any barriers (or risks) to success?		Observations									
ID	Factor	Description	ID	Concern	Description	ID	Obstacle/Challenge	Description	ID	Note					
F1			E1			B1			N1						
F2			E2			B2			N2						
F3			E3			B3			N3						
F4			E4			B4			N4						
F5			E5			B5			N5						